

Evaluating the carbon impact of research proposals, and its implication on grant allocation

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“The crisis that faces us in climate and biodiversity needs to be reflected in every grant application as a key element of ethical and societal responsibility.”

Many recommendations from the DRI Net Zero Scoping project propose that carbon impact of projects must be considered in the research proposal stage and even implemented as a requirement of grant allocation processes.

Currently, there is little or no requirement for researchers to consider the climate and sustainability impacts of their work. Furthermore, in most cases, staff do not have the tools and knowledge at hand to tackle this. Policies and requirements for net zero should be paired with adequate training to not just increase awareness and understanding of the implications of climate change and the net zero policy, but also to provide technical competence to deliver change.

As the tools, technology and knowledge are rapidly developing for a future where we can accurately quantify the carbon impact of our DRI use, it is expected that evaluation of environmental impact will become a requirement. We can take steps now to encourage a shift in the way that research and innovation is conducted. This prepares for DRI use that both delivers cutting edge innovation at the same time as carefully considering and mitigating the cost this has on our environment.

Grant assessment

The inclusion of an environmental impact statement within applications for research funding encourages researchers to consider the negative impact of their work and take steps to reduce it. This should include clear carbon and sustainability assessments and mitigating actions. Many projects from the Net Zero Scoping Report suggest this should be a mandated part of funding applications. Targeted funding for Net Zero projects are already driving behavioural change in parts of the community, showing that this incentive is effective.

Predicting the carbon consumption of a project may not be as straightforward as financial budgets, especially as the carbon intensity of the UK electricity grid is constantly changing. UKRI will need to develop tools to allow applicants a transparent and clear carbon content assessment of their proposals and projects to underpin this.

Carbon should be considered a limited resource in the same way as financial resources. Including environmental sustainability within funding assessment and award processes ensures that it is planned into the project from the outset.

There could be systems to reward work that reduces carbon footprints, and these systems should be clear at the time of awarding funding, for example by allowing grant holders to roll over unused financial budgets where there is a commitment to use such funds to further reduce carbon emissions. Researchers should be encouraged to report their positive environmental impact.

Furthermore, we must also adopt a common understanding of the balance between the negative impact of using resources to conduct research and the positive impact which research delivers. Mandating carbon assessments at the grant proposal stage forces us to think about this with every grant.

At this stage, a full environmental impact statement provided with each grant application is not realistic and may discriminate against smaller institutions with fewer tools to measure this. However, we do not need to wait for the technology for accurate measurement to think about ways we can reduce the carbon footprint of our work. Even crude estimates of carbon footprint and general steps taken to reduce environmental impact can fuel a paradigm shift in the way we think about the impacts of the work we do. This also prepares us for a future where full environmental impact assessment will be a reality in order to reach Net Zero DRI.

Ways to measure carbon impact

In order to request carbon and environmental assessments, a standard way of estimating carbon footprint and adequate guidance are required to assist researchers in evaluating these metrics. However, we need to act now, so learn-by-doing approaches even if informed by crude estimates of carbon footprint should be considered.

Constructing an Environmental Impact Assessment for DRI activities alongside standard Risk Assessments

Environmental impact assessments could be implemented like risk assessments for procurement and DRI activities. In many funding applications and ethics applications academics are required to include a 'Risk Assessment' for their research and reviewers can determine whether their research is deemed 'low risk', 'medium risk', or 'high risk'. This procedure could be adapted to assess the carbon footprint of planned research projects by using a 'Carbon Assessment' tool.

Categories would need to be carefully selected and include items like data storage, data sharing, equipment usage, conference travel etc. and a weighting would need to be assigned for each of the different categories.

For example, if in the funding application a researcher was requesting financial support for attending a conference abroad and they were flying, this would be categorised as 'high carbon'. If on the other hand the researcher was requesting support for conference fees but not requesting travel money because they are attending a conference virtually, this would be

deemed as 'low carbon'. Similarly, travelling to a conference within the UK using public transport would be considered 'medium carbon'. Conference travel would have a high weighting due to the carbon emissions of transport, compared to equipment usage, for example.

The application could then be assigned an overall 'Carbon Assessment' score (totalling all of the categories with the weighting calculated). Funders will then be able to assess the carbon footprint of the research project and feed back to the researchers and advise as to how to reduce it (if necessary).

This recommendation of environmental impact assessments comes from the User Behaviour Survey¹, a consortium project conducted as part of the Net Zero Scoping Project.

Collecting energy consumption data

This would require user-level energy monitoring in a specified format on all UKRI funded DRI, which could be incorporated into the funding and procurement process.

Grant allocations of national supercomputing and HPC services such as ARCHER2 and DiRAC have traditionally be awarded in units of compute time (e.g. node-hours) with users not informed, nor paying much attention to their energy use; and services not generally reporting breakdowns of energy use other than for total electricity charges. However ARCHER2 and DiRAC COSMA services already collect power and energy measurements for operational reasons. That information along with existing job accounting data means there is scope to reprocess this into useful energy metrics to enable informed decisions on the path to Net Zero.

There is potential conflict between the desire to minimise the carbon expenditure on DRI use at the individual project level and decisions made about scheduling jobs to minimise energy consumption at the collective facility level.

For instance, a climate modeller might wish their simulations to be run during periods of low carbon intensity energy supply to make best use of their carbon budget allocation. Whereas a facility manager might prefer to run climate model software during periods of high carbon intensity because the input output restrictions of the climate model software requires less energy draw for the CPU.

Making such a scheduler a community-driven development would increase DRI stakeholder engagement and drive trust in the system compared to a top-down imposed solution.

¹ McGuire, L. (2023). User Behaviour Survey Final Report: The motivators/enablers, and barriers to sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure use. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7827919>

Ways to reduce carbon impact

Conducting Net Zero Action Plans

Net Zero actions plans can be a useful tool for planning sustainable use of DRI from a project outset. Many of the skills and knowledge that will be needed to solve the net zero challenge already exist within our communities. Net zero action plans are a method to harness that power and empower individuals and communities to realise their potential as agents of the change that will enable great research to continue whilst we reduce our carbon footprint.

From the action plans developed within the Go-Zero workshop series, a recipe book has been put together with example action plans for achieving net zero. These can be adapted to individual projects using the 5W technique by asking the following questions: What aspects of your work are related to net zero targets? Who needs to take action to meet these net zero targets? When will these targets be achieved? Where can these changes be implemented? And Why would these methods/approaches work, or are there any barriers?

Sustainable computing training

Training provided to researchers on best practices regarding efficient DRI use empowers users to reduce the carbon footprint of their own work. This can also demonstrate consideration of efficient DRI use in research proposals.

This would involve training researchers in basic practices (e.g. software testing and review, DoE design) that will greatly improve the overall energy efficiency of their digital experiments. This could also include providing researchers with access to green software engineers to both help them with their practice and improve the energy efficiency of their code.

A database for green computing could be set up to act as a repository of detailed documentation about what has been done to increase energy efficiency in past projects. Such a resource could prove a valuable starting point for DRI stakeholders looking to optimise new codes. Similarly to an ethics review or animal use review in research applications, consulting this database for green computing could be made a mandatory part of the grant application process to show that applicants are familiar with established measures to decrease the footprint of their intended computations.

Adopting Efficient Frameworks

Institutions should adopt the LEAF (Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework)² for digital infrastructure.

² [Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework \(LEAF\) \(bath.ac.uk\)](https://www.bath.ac.uk/leaf/)

Paradigm shift in workplace policies

It is recommended that sustainability practices are built into workplace policies to enable sustainable behaviours to be integrated into daily work rather than being perceived as an additional burden.

Supporting recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)³. A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 44: Pressure could be applied from funding bodies to request an assessment of carbon-impact for each proposal and to perform life cycle analysis. To do this there's a requirement for the developments of tools and information to help people include these data in proposals. Funding councils could ask proposals to consider efficiency and plan for reducing footprint.

Recommendation 47: Include carbon costs within the assessment process and planning of research grants.

Recommendation 122: All funders to include a carbon assessment for all grant applications.

Recommendation 134: Institutions should adopt the LEAF (Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework) for digital infrastructure.

Recommendation 154: Mandate the inclusion of an environmental impact statement, along with mitigating actions, within applications for research funding.

Recommendation 37: Commitment to reporting energy consumption data to users.

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Recommendation 33: Develop a resource allocation policy that allows users to use resources in a more carbon-efficient way (e.g. longer runtime for less carbon emissions) and allow for "spot" workloads that can be deallocated when carbon intensity is high or when PUE increases

Recommendation 87: Positive environmental impact from users. Researchers should be encouraged to report their positive environmental impact.

Recommendation 122: UKRI/all funders to include a 'Carbon Assessment' for all grant applications. In many funding applications and ethics applications academics are required to include a 'Risk Assessment' for their research and reviewers can determine whether their research is deemed 'low risk', 'medium risk', or 'high risk'. This procedure could be adapted to assess the carbon footprint of planned research projects by using a 'Carbon Assessment' tool.

³ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>